

Polymerase and Hydrolytic Activities of Purified Goat Brain Cysteine Proteinase Dipeptidyl Peptidase I

SURESH PAL, NEERA RAGHAV, RAMESH C. KAMBOJ and HARI SINGH*

Biochemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 11 September 1991, accepted 7 February 1992

The purified goat brain dipeptidyl peptidase I (DPPI) catalysed the hydrolysis of substrate Gly-Arg-4-methoxy-2-naphthylamide maximally at pH 6.0. At pH 7.0, it showed both hydrolysis as well as polymerization of this substrate while at pH 8.0 the enzyme exhibited only polymerase activity. The adrenocorticotrophic hormone was cleaved sequentially from the N-terminal removing the dipeptide moieties. The enzyme hydrolysed gastrin tetrapeptide amide, Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂, an active part of a gastrointestinal peptide hormone, into Trp-Met and Asp-Phe-NH₂ fragments at pH 6.0 showing no polymerase activity at pH 8.0. Another model tetrapeptide Ala-Ala-Ala-Ala was also hydrolysed into two fragments of Ala-Ala, but its N-blocked analog Ac-Ala-Ala-Ala-Ala was not cleaved at all establishing thereby the requirement of free NH₂ group at the N-terminal end of a peptide/polypeptide. The tripeptide substrate Ala-Ala-Ala was also not hydrolysed proving that tripeptides are not good substrates for goat brain DPPI.

Dipeptidyl peptidase I (DPPI) (EC.3.4.14.1) formerly called cathepsin C has been shown to cleave several peptides and hormones like glucagon, secretin, β -corticotrophic hormone¹, B-chain and des-Phe-B-chain of oxidised bovine insulin, A-chain of oxidised bovine insulin² and angiotensin II^{3,4}. All these studies were conducted with DPPI preparations obtained either from liver or spleen. No attempt has been made till now to purify and characterise the enzyme DPPI from brain. Brain is very important organ of the mammalian body and contains proteolytic enzymes which act on the native proteins present therein⁵. Brain being the master organ conducts and coordinates the multifarious functions of the body. We report here the degradation of gastrin-NH₂ (Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂), ACTH (1-10) and (Ala)₄ by purified goat brain DPPI. The N-blocked model peptide Ac(Ala)₄ was also examined for degradation. The polymerase activity of the enzyme obtained from brain has also been described.

Results and Discussion

Dipeptidyl peptidase I (DPPI) purified from goat brain hydrolysed the synthetic substrate Gly-Arg-NNapOMe maximally at pH 6.0 (Fig. 1). This pH optimum of 6.0 has been reported by McDonald and Schwabe⁶ and Mettrione *et al.*⁷ for rat liver and beef spleen DPPI respectively. However, Paszkowski *et al.*⁸ reported a lower pH optima of 5.5 for rabbit lung DPPI. The polymerase activity of goat brain DPPI was determined at different pHs in the range 5.0-9.0 using Gly-Arg-NNapOMe (-NNapOMe, -6-methoxy-2-naphthylamide). The enzyme catalysed the polymerization of the substrate maximally at pH 9.0 (Fig. 2). At pH 7.0, the enzyme exhibited both hydrolytic as well as polymerase activity, but at pH 6.0, only hydrolytic activity was observed (Scheme 1). Goat brain

enzyme gave two polymerization products which were not identified due to the non-availability of the standard marker polymer. Paszkowski *et al.*⁸

Fig. 1. Determination of pH-optima for goat brain DPPI using Gly-Arg-NNapOMe as substrate. The enzyme activity was measured at different pHs, i.e. 2.90, 3.50, 4.00 (0.1 M sodium formate), 4.51, 5.01, 5.50, 5.72 and 6.02 (0.1 M sodium succinate), 6.21, 6.48, 7.00, 7.50 (0.1 M sodium phosphate), 8.00, 8.50, 9.00 and 9.45 (0.1 M tris-HCl) respectively. The enzyme activity has been expressed in nanomoles of 4-methoxy-2-naphthylamine released per min per mg protein.

Fig. 2. Hydrolytic and polymerase activity of goat brain DPPI with Gly-Arg-NNapOMe. Goat brain DPPI (30 μ g) incubated with 3.74 mg of Gly-Arg-NNapOMe at pHs, i.e. pH 6.0, 7.0, 8.0 and 9.0 for 90 min at 37°. The hydrolytic/polymerase products were separated on tlc in solvent system n-butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15) on silica gel plate (20 \times 40 cm). Lane 1, 4-methoxy-2-naphthylamine (R_f = 0.941), Gly-Arg-NNapOMe (R_f = 0.647) and Gly-Arg (R_f = 0.118); Lane 2, hydrolytic products obtained at pH 6.0; Lane 3, hydrolytic/polymerase products obtained at pH 7.0; Lane 4, hydrolytic/polymerase products obtained at pH 8.0; Lane 5, hydrolytic polymerase product(s) obtained at pH 9.0.

Fig. 3. Tlc separation of hydrolytic products of gastrin tetrapeptide amide by DPPI. The enzyme DPPI (30 μ g) was incubated with 3 mg of Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂ at pH 6.0 and 8.0 at 37° for 3 h. After stopping the reaction by freezing at 0°, the products of hydrolysis were separated by tlc on a silica gel plate (20 \times 40 cm) in a solvent system n-butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15); Lane 1, Trp-Met (15). Asp-Phe-NH₂ (R_f = 0.722); Lane 2, Trp-Met (R_f = 0.722); Lane 3, Asp-Phe-NH₂ (R_f = 0.535); Lane 4, hydrolytic products obtained by the action of DPPI on Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂ at pH 6.0; Lane 5, product(s) obtained by incubation of Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂ at pH 8.0 with DPPI. The spots were developed by ninhydrin spray.

peptidase of cleaving and synthesizing the peptide bonds confers unique distinction on this enzyme. Hence, this enzyme may be helpful in the production and inactivation of endogenous bioactive peptides (acting as hormones) present in the brain.

Experimental

Gly-Arg-4-methoxy-2-naphthylamide gastrin

tetrapeptide amide (Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂), Trp-Met and Asp-Phe-NH₂ (all Bachem Feinchemikalein), Fast garnet GBC (*o*-aminoazotoluene diazonium salt), *p*-chloromercuribenzoic acid, (Ala)₄, Ac-(Ala)₄ and (Ala)₃ (all Sigma) and ninhydrin (Loba) were used. All other chemicals used in the experiments were of highest purity available.

The dipeptidyl peptidase I activity was measured

using Gly-Arg-NNapOMe as the substrate at pH 6.0 colourimetrically¹¹. The enzyme was purified from goat brain¹² by preparing acetone powder, homogenisation, acid-autolysis at pH 4.2 overnight at room temperature, 30–70% ammonium sulphate fractionation, molecular sieve chromatography on Sephadex G-100 column, heat-treatment at pH 5.5

anion-exchange chromatography at pH 6.8. The purity of the enzyme was established through electrophoreses at pH 4.5¹³, pH 8.3¹⁴ and in denaturing conditions in presence of SDS at pH 7.2¹⁵.

To determine the hydrolytic/polymerase activity of the purified goat brain DPPI, it was incubated

Fig. 4. Hydrolysis of $(Ala)_4$, $Ac-(Ala)_4$ and $(Ala)_3$ by goat brain DPPI. DPPI (30 μ g) was incubated with 3 mg each of $(Ala)_4$, $Ac-(Ala)_4$ and $(Ala)_3$ separately, at pH 6.0 at 37° for 3 h. The hydrolytic products were then identified by tlc in the solvent system n-butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15) on silica gel plate (20 \times 40 cm). Lane 1, Ala-Ala-Ala-Ala (R_f = 0.292), Ala-Ala (R_f = 0.416); Lane 2, Ala-Ala-Ala (R_f = 0.333); Lane 3, hydrolytic product of Ala-Ala-Ala-Ala by brain DPPI; Lane 4, hydrolytic product(s) of Ala-Ala-Ala and Lane 5, hydrolytic product(s) of N-blocked Ac-Ala-Ala-Ala-Ala (R_f = 0.569).

Fig. 5. Degradation of adrenocorticotrophic hormone (Ser-Tyr-Ser-Met-Glu-His-Phe-Arg-Trp-Gly) by goat brain DPPI. The purified enzyme DPPI (30 μ g) was incubated with ACTH (1.0 mg) in a 0.1 M sodium succinate buffer pH 6.0 containing 20 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA and 10 mM 2-mercaptoethanol at 37° for 3 h. The hydrolytic action was stopped by adding formic acid. The hydrolytic products were separated by tlc in the solvent system n-butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15) on silica gel plate (20 \times 40 cm). The products and standards were identified by spraying ninhydrin solution. Lane 1, Trp-Gly (R_f = 0.639), ACTH (R_f = 0.444); Glu-His (R_f = 0.111); Lane 2, Ser-Tyr (R_f = 0.5); Lane 3, Ser-Met (R_f = 0.430); Lane 4, Phe-Arg; (R_f = 0.347); Lane 5, hydrolytic products of ACTH.

at 65° in presence of 2 mM 2-mercaptoethanol, CM-Sephadex C-50 cation-exchange chromatography at pH 5.6 and pH 5.0 and DEAE-Sephadex A-50

with substrate Gly-Arg-NNapOMe at different pHs, i.e. 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0 and 9.0 separately at 37° for 1h. The reaction was terminated by formic acid. This hydrolysate was then applied on the activated silica gel plate. The standard substances Gly-Arg, 4-methoxy-2-naphthylamine were also applied on the same silica gel plate (20 × 40 cm). This plate was run in the solvent system butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15) for 24 h. Then it was dried, sprayed with ninhydrin solution (1% ninhydrin in acetone mixed with 5 ml of 88 mM cadmium acetate in acetic acid solution) and was developed by heating in an oven at 110°. The upper portion of the plate was exposed to iodine vapour to develop the spots for 4-methoxy-2-naphthylamine.

The degradation of Gastrin-NH₂ (Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂) was established by tlc. The peptide hormone was subjected to fragmentation by purified goat brain DPPI at pH 6.0 and 8.0 by incubating at 37° and the resulting hydrolysate was then applied on silica gel plate along with standards Trp-Met-Asp-Phe-NH₂, Trp-Met and Asp-Phe-NH₂. The solvent system used and development of spots by ninhydrin were similar as above. The degradation of (Ala)₄, Ac(Ala)₄ and (Ala)₃ by DPPI was established likewise. A decapeptide ACTH (adrenocorticotrophic hormone) (Ser-Tyr-Ser-Met-Glu-His-Phe-Arg-Trp-Met) was also subjected to degradation by purified goat brain DPPI at pH 6.0 at 37°. The reaction was stopped by formic acid and this hydrolysate was applied on the freshly prepared silica gel plate along with standard Ser-Tyr, Ser-Met, Glu-His, Phe-Arg and Trp-Met. The plate was run in n-butanol-formic acid-water (70 : 15 : 15). When the solvent reached the top, the plate was dried in air

and sprayed with ninhydrin and developed as described above.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. S. P. Singh, Chairman, Department of Chemistry for facilities. Two of the authors (S.P. and N.R.) thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for NET Fellowships.

References

1. J. K. McDONALD, P. X. CALLAHAN, B. B. ZEITMAN and S. ELLIS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1969, 244, 6199.
2. J. K. McDONALD, P. X. CALLAHAN and S. ELLIS, *Methods Enzymology*, 1972, 25, 272.
3. J. K. McDONALD, B. B. ZEITMAN, P. X. CALLAHAN and S. ELLIS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 249, 234.
4. J. K. McDONALD, B. B. ZEITMAN and S. ELLIS, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 1972, 46, 62.
5. N. MARKS in "Peptides in Neurobiology", ed. H. GAINER, Plenum, New York, 1977, p. 22.
6. J. K. McDONALD and C. SCHWABF in "Proteinases in Mammalian Cells and Tissues", ed. A. J. BARRETT, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1977, p. 314.
7. R. M. METRIONE, A. G. NEVES and J. S. FRUTON, *Biochemistry*, 1966, 5, 1597.
8. A. PASZKOWSKI, H. SINGH and G. KALNITSKY, *Acta Biochem. Pol.*, 1983, 30, 363.
9. K. K. NILSSON and J. S. FRUTON, *Biochemistry*, 1984, 3, 1220.
10. J. K. McDONALD, B. B. ZEITMAN, T. J. REILLY and S. ELLIS, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1969, 244, 2693.
11. A. J. BARRETT in "Proteinases in Mammalian Cells and Tissues", ed. A. J. BARRETT, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1977, p. 209.
12. S. PAL, Ph.D. Thesis, Kurukshetra University, 1991.
13. R. A. REISFELD, U. J. LEWIS and D. E. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1962, 195, 281.
14. B. J. DAVIS, *Ann. N Y Acad. Sci.*, 1964, 121, 404.
15. K. WEBER and M. OSBORN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1969, 244, 4406.